

The Reaction of Potassium Permanganate with Potassium Ferrocyanide and Some Binary Mixtures in Presence of Fluoride Ions*

H. A. DESSOKI, M. G. ALLAM and A. M. HAMMAM

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Zagazig University, Benha, A. R. Egypt

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The reactions of potassium permanganate with potassium ferrocyanide and binary mixtures of ferrous-mercurous (1), ferrocyanide-mercurous (2) and ferrous-ferrocyanide (3) have been studied potentiometrically in acid medium containing fluoride ions. For potassium ferrocyanide, good results are obtained at 0.018-1.8 N H_2SO_4 in presence of 0.238-0.357 M NaF at temperature range 25-50°. But in the case of the mixtures, the optimum acidities are 0.315 N H_2SO_4 (2, 3) and 0.22 N (1) in presence of 0.357 M NaF at 25°. 125-503 mg of ferrocyanide can be determined with high accuracy. The constituents of the mixtures can be titrated in presence of each other. The difficulty of precipitation of manganese(II) ferrocyanide can be overcome by keeping the reduction product of $KMnO_4$ as complex Mn(III) fluoride.

THE reaction between $KMnO_4$ and ferrocyanide in acid medium was studied by De Beer and Hjort¹. Kolthoff² titrated ferrocyanide at concentration less than 0.02 M by comparing the colour at the end point with that of ferrocyanide. Enough acid should be present to prevent the precipitation of manganous ferrocyanide. Potentiometric titration of ferrocyanide in alkaline medium was reported by Issa and Azin³.

The monovalent mercury⁴ and bivalent iron⁵ can be titrated quantitatively with $KMnO_4$ in presence of fluoride ions. Ferrous iron reduces $KMnO_4$ under these conditions in two steps with formation of Mn(III) and Mn(II). However, monovalent mercury does not effect the reduction quantitatively to the Mn(II) step. This difference is obviously related to the reducing power of the different species which is known to depend on the redox potential values of the system concerned which amount to 0.92, 0.771 and 0.36 volt, respectively⁶. It is therefore of interest to find out how binary mixtures of these species and ferrocyanide behave in their oxidation with $KMnO_4$.

Experimental

Potassium permanganate, potassium ferrocyanide, mercurous nitrate and ferrous sulphate solutions were prepared from chemically pure salts and standardised according to recommended procedures. 4.5 M H_2SO_4 and 0.476 M NaF were also prepared from chemically pure products. The titration equipment is the same as described earlier⁷.

Results and Discussion

Reaction between potassium permanganate and potassium ferrocyanide:

The titration curves of ferrocyanide with $KMnO_4$ in absence of F^- ions and acidity of 0.045 M H_2SO_4

includes one inflection corresponding to the reduction of $KMnO_4$ to Mn(II). This inflection amounts to 230 mV per 0.05 ml of the titrant. In presence of NaF of different molarities (0.119-0.357 M) a second inflection appears, representing the oxidation of the originally produced Mn(II) to Mn(III). Under these conditions the second end point coincides with the theoretical value in presence of NaF (0.238 to 0.357 M) and occurs somewhat earlier at 0.119 M NaF. The first inflection occurs about 14% earlier than expected on the basis of the formation of Mn(II). This is obviously due to partial precipitation of ferrocyanide as the Mn(II) salt. However, this precipitate undergoes oxidation at the second step together with the initially formed Mn(II). This fact finds support from the effect of acidity on the titration process. As the acidity of the solution is increased the first end point retreats slowly until it coincides with the theoretical value for the Mn(II) step at 0.45 M H_2SO_4 . The second end point always coincides with that expected for the Mn(III) step. At higher acidities (0.675 M) the second inflection disappears and the curve is restricted to the first step.

At temperatures between 25-40° and at an acidity of 0.02 M, the two inflections do not deviate from the theoretical values. At 50° the Mn(II) step approaches the theoretical values probably as a result of the increased solubility of the Mn(II) ferrocyanide. The second end point is attained earlier than the expected value due to the partial decomposition of $KMnO_4$ at high temperature.

Titration of different quantities of ferrocyanide can be achieved when the second end point is taken into consideration. The first end point shows larger negative errors on increasing the concentration of ferrocyanide. The amount of ferrocyanide precipitated apparently increases with the increase

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in the concentrations of the reactants—Mn(II) and ferrocyanide.

The redox potentials of the ferric/ferrocyanide couple and that of Mn(III)/Mn(II) couple under various conditions were evaluated from the titration curves (Figs. 1 and 2). The data in Table 1

Fig. 1. Titration of 0.00942 N $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ with 0.0922 N $KMnO_4$ in presence of NaF (0.357 M) and H_2SO_4 of different molarities.

A - 0.009 M, B - 0.0225 M, C - 0.045 M, D - 0.225 M, E - 0.45 M, F - 0.675 M and G - 0.90 M H_2SO_4 .

indicate an increase of the formal potential with rise of acidity and decrease of fluoride ion concentration. They are not affected much by temperature or concentration of the reactants.

Titration of a mixture containing Fe(II) and Hg_2^{2+} :

The titration curve of this mixture (Fig. 3) is characterised by two inflections, the first of which is small and amounts to 25-35 mV. The second inflection is larger and amounts to 170-230 mV. The first step corresponds to the oxidation of

Fig. 2. Titration of different molarities of $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ with 0.0922 N $KMnO_4$ at optimum conditions. A - 0.00842 N, B - 0.00547 N, C - 0.00684 N, D - 0.0108 N and E - 0.0137 N $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$.

Fig. 3. Titration of a mixture containing Fe^{2+} and Hg_2^{2+} with 0.0922 N $KMnO_4$ in presence of 0.225 N H_2SO_4 and 0.357 N NaF. A - 0.000828 N Fe^{2+} and 0.006528 N Hg_2^{2+} , B - 0.001656 N Fe^{2+} and 0.006528 N Hg_2^{2+} and C - 0.001656 N Fe^{2+} and 0.003264 N Hg_2^{2+} .

TABLE 1—TITRATION OF $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ WITH 0.0922 N $KMnO_4$ IN PRESENCE OF 0.357 M NaF AT 25°

$K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$		Volume of $KMnO_4$ consumed (ml)		Theoretical end point (ml)		Error		Inflection at end point (mV/0.05 ml)		Formal redox potential (V)	
ml	mg	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	1	2
5	125	3.51	4.65	3.75	4.69	-6.41	-0.85	112	88	0.474	0.834
8	201	4.92	7.50	6.02	7.51	-18.10	-0.13	130	74	0.476	0.842
10	251	6.50	9.95	7.50	9.98	-13.33	-0.32	146	58	0.449	0.842
15	377	9.41	13.96	11.23	14.07	-16.21	-0.78	152	46	0.469	0.848
20	503	13.00	18.60	15.01	18.76	-13.40	-0.85	158	29	0.464	0.852
Acidity											
ml	M										
0.2	0.009	3.41	4.68	3.75	4.69	-9.10	-0.21	176	70	0.450	0.844
0.5	0.0225	3.56	4.67	3.75	4.69	-5.33	-0.42	218	68	0.453	0.862
1.0	0.045	3.61	4.65	3.75	4.69	-3.73	-0.84	308	32	0.475	0.973
5	0.135	3.65	4.65	3.75	4.69	-2.67	-0.84	312	20	0.498	0.994
10	0.225	3.75	4.63	3.75	4.69	nil	-1.26	377	18	0.550	1.103
15	0.45	3.75	—	3.75	4.69	nil	—	395	—	0.614	—
20	0.9	3.72	—	3.75	4.69	-0.80	—	400	—	0.688	—

Normality of $KMnO_4$ on the basis of valency change $Mn^{7+} \rightarrow Mn^{2+}$.
 (a) $MnO_4^- \rightarrow Mn^{2+}$; (b) $Mn^{3+} \rightarrow Mn^{2+}$.
 (1) $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}/[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ system; (2) Mn^{3+}/Mn^{2+} system.

ferrous iron since the formal redox potential depicted from this step amounts to about 617 mV which is in harmony with the values obtained in the titration of ferrous iron alone⁵. The end point, as is evident from Table 2, is attained when $KMnO_4$ is reduced to the Mn(II) step.

The second inflection in the titration curve represents oxidation of mercurous mercury and the formed manganese(II) whereby MnO_4^- is reduced to Mn(III). The redox potential value, as evaluated from the second inflection, amounts to about 900 mV which approximates that of the Hg^{2+}/Hg_2^{2+} couple under the prevailing experimental conditions. The second end point coincides fairly well with theoretical values based on complete oxidation of Fe(II) and Hg(I) whereby MnO_4^- is reduced to the manganic state. The separation of the two steps of reduction is in harmony with the apparent difference in the redox potential of the two systems involved in the reaction. The success of the titration is confirmed by varying the amounts of the two reductants in the mixture and also by titrating the separate constituents alone under the same experimental conditions. The results depicted in Table 2 are in harmony with these speculation.

Titration of a mixture containing ferrocyanide and mercurous mercury :

The curves obtained in the titration of this mixture are approximately similar to those obtained in the case of ferrous iron and mercurous mercury and obviously represent the same sequence of the reaction steps (Fig. 4). The first inflection represents oxidation of ferrocyanide whereby MnO_4^- is reduced to Mn(II). The latter, together with monovalent mercury, is oxidised in the second step whereby MnO_4^- is reduced to Mn(III). The occurrence of these two steps is in harmony with the redox potential values of the systems involved, which amount to 0.432 and 0.93 V for the $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}/[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}$ and the Hg^{2+} systems, respectively. The end points (Table 3) coincide fairly well with the theoretical values for the

Fig. 4. Titration of a mixture of 0.0684 N $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ and 0.0816 N Hg_2^{2+} in presence of 0.815 N H_2SO_4 and 0.857 N NaF.

A - 0.002786 N $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ and 0.006528 N Hg_2^{2+} ;
 B - 0.00546 N $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ and 0.006528 N Hg_2^{2+} and
 C - 0.00548 N $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ and 0.003264 N Hg_2^{2+} .

different mixtures titrated. The mechanism of the reaction is confirmed by comparing the titration curve of the mixture with the titration curves of the separate constituents.

Titration of a mixture containing ferrous iron and potassium ferrocyanide :

The titration curves of this mixtures (Fig. 5) show two inflections. The first step as gathered from the redox potential of the two systems involved amounting to 150 and 260 mV, respectively, indicates oxidation of ferrocyanide whereby MnO_4^- is reduced to Mn(II). The inflection involves oxidation of both ferrous iron and the manganous manganese produced in the first step. These speculations are confirmed by the coincidence of the end point with the theoretical and comparison of the curves of the mixture with those of the separate constituents. The data in Table 4 are in conformity with these facts.

Contrary to expectations, ferrous iron did not produce a step corresponding to the reduction of

TABLE 2—TITRATION OF 0.0457 N Fe^{2+} SOLUTION AND 0.0816 N Hg_2^{2+} SOLUTION WITH 0.0923 N $KMnO_4$ IN PRESENCE OF 0.957 M NaF

Mixture	H_2SO_4 9 N (ml)	Theoretical end point (ml)				Exp. end point (ml)		Error %	Max. inflec. (mV/ 0.05 ml)		Formal redox potential (V)		
		Fe^{2+}		Hg_2^{2+}		1st Inflection	2nd Inflection		1st Inflection	2nd Inflection	Fe^{2+}/Fe^{3+} system	Mn^{2+}/Mn^{3+} system	
		Mn ²⁺	Mn ³⁺	Mn ²⁺	Mn ³⁺								
4 ml Fe^{2+}	2.5	2.06	2.57	7.08	8.85	2.07	11.45	+0.48	+0.26	23	190	0.747	0.864
8 ml Hg_2^{2+}	10.0	2.06	2.57	7.08	8.85	2.05	11.99	-0.48	-0.26	22	195	0.803	0.939
8 ml Fe^{2+}	2.5	4.12	5.14	7.08	8.85	4.10	13.95	-0.24	-0.38	30	175	0.738	0.850
8 ml Hg_2^{2+}	10.0	4.12	5.14	7.08	8.85	4.09	13.93	-0.78	-0.48	28	230	0.742	0.877
4 ml Fe^{2+}	2.5	4.12	5.14	3.54	4.34	4.10	9.56	-0.49	+0.84	28	170	0.792	0.837
4 ml Hg_2^{2+}	10.0	4.12	5.14	3.54	4.34	4.08	9.55	-0.97	+0.74	35	180	0.707	0.908
8 ml Fe^{2+}	2.5	4.12	5.14	-	-	4.10	5.12	-0.34	-0.39	310	25	0.617	1.264
8 ml Hg_2^{2+}	2.5	-	-	7.08	8.85	-	8.89	-	-0.45	-	205	-	0.930 [§]

* Mn^{2+}/Fe^{2+}

** Mn^{2+} (total)

§ $Hg(II)/Hg(I)$ system

TABLE 3—TITRATION OF MIXTURES OF 0.068 N [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ AND 0.0816 N Hg₂²⁺ WITH 0.0922 N KMnO₄ IN PRESENCE OF 0.357M NaF

Mixture	H ₂ SO ₄ 9 N (ml)	Theoretical end point (ml)				Exp. end point (ml)		Error %		Max. inflec. mV/0.05 ml		F. redox pot- ential (V)	
		[Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻		Hg ₂ ²⁺		1st	2nd	1st	2nd	1st	2nd	[Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻ /	Mn ²⁺
		Mn ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Inflection		Inflection		Inflection		[Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻ /	Mn ²⁺
4 ml [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻	2.5	3.0	3.78	7.08	8.85	2.98	12.60	-0.67	-0.24	170	50	0.604	1.070
+8 ml Hg ₂ ²⁺	10	"	"	"	"	3.98	12.52	+0.67	-0.87	70	28	0.782	1.182
8 ml [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻	2.5	6.02	7.51	"	"	5.99	16.4	-0.49	-0.36	162	32	0.550	1.144
+8 ml Hg ₂ ²⁺	10	"	"	"	"	5.97	16.34	-0.83	-0.73	205	38	0.502	1.070
8 ml [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻	2.5	"	"	3.56	4.45	5.96	11.87	-0.99	+0.75	220	30	0.517	1.072
+4 ml Hg ₂ ²⁺	10	"	"	"	"	6.01	11.98	-0.16	+0.17	218	28	0.546	1.045
8 ml [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻	2.5	6.02	7.51	"	"	6.03	7.54	+0.16	+0.40	325	38	0.482	1.006
8 ml Hg ₂ ²⁺	2.5	—	—	7.08	8.85	—	8.91	—	+0.68	—	205	—	0.980 [§]

* Mn²⁺/Fe²⁺

** Mn²⁺ (total)

§ Hg(II)/Hg(I) system

TABLE 4—TITRATION OF MIXTURE OF 0.0684 N [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ AND 0.0457 N Fe²⁺ WITH 0.0922 N KMnO₄ IN PRESENCE OF 0.357 M NaF

Mixture	H ₂ SO ₄ 9 N (ml)	Theoretical end point (ml)				Exp. end point (ml)		Error %		Inflection mV/0.05 ml		F. redox pot- ential (V)	
		FeSO ₄		[Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻		1st	2nd	1st	2nd	1st	2nd	[Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻ /	Mn ²⁺
		Mn ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Inflection		Inflection		Inflection		[Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻ /	Mn ²⁺
4 ml Fe ²⁺	0.5	2.06	2.57	6.02	7.51	5.97	10.0	-0.85	-0.79	150	30	0.496	1.01
8 ml [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻	3.5	2.06	2.57	6.02	7.51	6.00	10.05	-0.84	-0.29	220	40	0.457	1.076
8 ml Fe ²⁺	0.5	4.12	5.15	6.02	7.51	5.99	12.6	-0.51	-0.47	238	45	0.482	1.019
8 ml [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻	3.5	4.12	5.15	6.02	7.51	6.0	12.55	-0.94	-0.87	255	40	0.446	1.067
8 ml Fe ²⁺	0.5	4.12	5.15	3.0	3.78	3.02	8.90	-0.67	-0.34	260	35	0.398	1.084
4 ml [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻	3.5	4.12	5.15	3.0	3.78	3.01	8.89	-0.83	-0.45	375	30	0.445	1.082
8 ml Fe ²⁺	0.5	4.12	5.15	6.02	7.51	6.0	12.6	-0.84	-0.48	237	40	0.397	0.999
8 ml [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻	1.0	4.12	5.15	6.02	7.51	5.99	12.58	-0.51	-0.64	239	38	0.417	1.007
2.5	4.12	5.15	6.02	7.51	6.0	12.56	-0.94	-0.80	240	40	0.418	1.044	
5.0	4.12	5.15	6.02	7.51	5.97	12.55	-0.85	-0.88	240	38	0.427	1.107	
10.0	4.12	5.15	6.02	7.51	5.98	12.58	-0.68	-1.04	242	36	0.467	1.129	
8 ml [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻	0.5	—	—	6.02	7.51	6.01	7.50	-0.17	-0.13	295	30	0.482	1.109
8 ml Fe ²⁺	0.5	4.12	5.15	—	—	4.09	5.12	-0.72	-0.58	310	25	0.612 [§]	1.252

* Mn²⁺/[Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻

** Mn²⁺ (total)

§ Fe(III)/Fe(II) system

Fig. 5. Titration of 0.0684 N [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ and 0.0457 N Fe²⁺ with 0.0922 N KMnO₄ in presence of 0.315 N H₂SO₄ and 0.357 N NaF.

A - 0.000828 N Fe²⁺ and 0.00543 N [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻,
 B - 0.001656 N Fe²⁺ and 0.00543 N [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ and
 C - 0.001656 N Fe²⁺ and 0.00273 N [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻.

MnO₄⁻ to Mn(II) state as occurs with pure ferrous solution, in spite of the relatively low potential of

the Fe(III)/Fe(II) system. The potential corresponding to the second step amounts to 1 volt, a value very close to that of the Mn(III)/Mn(II) couple. The absence of a step corresponding to Fe(III)/Fe(II) system can be explained by the interaction of the formed ferricyanide with the ferrous iron present to form Turnbull's blue. The latter apparently undergoes oxidation at a relatively higher potential than that of the ferric/ferrous system.

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